

Digital Humanities and Inclusive Librarianship: Designing a Collaborative, Multi-lingual, Skos-compliant Linked Open Vocabulary for LGBTQIA+

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Abstract

In simple words digital humanities indicates application of digital tools and technologies in the accomplishments of humanities computing, but demands additional responsibilities from LIS professionals in ensuring digital inclusiveness and in developing collaborative platform for domain modeling in different areas of humanities. This research work, in line of the advocacy given by the domain experts, attempts to create a collaborative, multilingual, standards compliant linked open vocabulary system for LGBTQIA+ domain by the application of open source software and open standards. The design part includes two layers – a) for organizing the Skos-compliant domain-specific vocabulary, and b) for providing access to the vocabulary as developed through a Skos-compliant browser to support multilingual browsing and searching. The tools and the methods adopted to port an existing LGBTQIA+ vocabulary (Homosaurus) into the proposed collaborative and multilingual framework are discussed in detail. The methodology as demonstrated may be extended to accommodate other domain-specific vocabularies and classification systems inside the proposed RDF supported and Skos-compliant framework.

Keywords: VocBench; Skosmos; SKOS; Linked open vocabulary; GraphDB; Fuseki; SemanticTurkey; LGBTQIA

1.Introduction

Lisa Spiro, the then Director of the National Institute for Technology in Liberal Education, pointed out five important facets of digital humanities way back in 2011, which are still very relevant. These are as follows: a) improve access to cultural information; b) use tools to access cultural data; c) transform scholarly communication with digital research tools; d) improve teaching and learning with ICT-enabled tools and techniques; and e) have an impact on the public (Spiro, 2011). These directions provided by Spiro in 2011 not only correspond to the spirit

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of the five laws of library science, but they also influenced many active minds to include digital humanities issues as top trends in academic libraries in 2012 (ACRL, 2012). Digital humanities (DH) is a loosely defined field of study, but almost all the definitions emphasize making, connecting, interpreting, collaborating, plurality, and investigation of human culture by applying digital technologies (Burdick et al., 2013; Jeffrey, 2014; Liu, 2013; Multitudes, 2015). In this context, Hartsell-Gundy and his team opined in their seminal contribution (Hartsell-Gundy et al, 2015) that digital humanities or “humanities computing” goes beyond the application of digital tools in research methods in the humanities and leads to better opportunities in domain modeling.

For example, subject librarians (including indexers, cataloguers, and classifiers) by using digital humanities tools and techniques may collaborate with subject specialists to design efficient knowledge organization systems (KOS) like depth schedules of classification, vocabulary control systems at micro-level, domain ontologies etc. In a similar note, an OCLC report entitled “Does every research library need a digital humanities center?” explained how library professionals can help subject specialists increase their own knowledge and expertise through better domain modeling of a given knowledge area through the application of digital humanities principles (Schaffner & Erway, 2014). Digital humanities cannot operate in isolation, and is essentially a team work of scholars, technologists, and librarians. Library professionals, apart from building the collection, understanding the research needs of the subject specialists, and ensuring access to organized resources, generally mediate the team members on the basis of their domain modeling skills and technological expertise (Gibson, Ladd, & Presnell, 2015; Nanditha, 2020; Kamada, 2010; Kear & Joranson, 2018).

This research work concentrates on three major facets of digital humanities where library professionals can contribute significantly (as proposed by domain experts) – a) inclusivity; b) domain modeling on the basis of semantic web standards; and c) development of a collaborative KOS (knowledge organization system) framework by the application of open source digital tools, where library professionals and subject specialists can contribute and interact seamlessly. The term “inclusivity” is defined by the Oxford English Dictionary as “the practice or policy of including people who might otherwise be excluded or marginalized, such as those who have physical or mental disabilities or members of minority groups.” The term “domain modeling indicates the activities of detecting and defining important domain-specific terms, including establishing relationships among the identified terms. In other words, it is a method for describing and modeling real-world things and their interactions that together define a given domain space. The semantic web standards here mean that each term is represented against a URI, terms have well-defined relationships, values are stored as RDF triples, and SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System)—a W3C standard—is to be applied to express a concept scheme as an RDF graph (Figure 1). The collaborative framework ensures availability of the entire vocabulary as a web entity for adding, editing, translating, excluding, and including terms/concepts/relationships on a global-scale to the people registered and having proper credentials and privileges.

2. Background

In view of the discussion in the previous section, this research work aims to develop a multilingual and Skos-compliant thesaurus in the domain of LGBTQIA+ to support inclusivity and to develop a collaborative space to create a dynamic KOS for the domain. This platform may achieve two goals—a) to overcome the inherent weakness of the KOSs of the library domain in organizing LGBTQIA related documents; and b) to help domain experts in creating a global-scale collaboration to develop the KOS as a tool to support research activities related to different aspects of LGBTQIA.

Figure 1: Graph structure of concepts relationships in SKOS model

2.1. What went wrong with the KOSs in libraries for LGBTQIA+ ?

The commonly used Knowledge Organization Systems (KOS) in libraries of any type or size in the world (like LCSH and DDC) are sexist and homophobic, and the conventional approach towards classification and cataloguing is still Eurocentric, Christocentric, heterosexual, and patriarchal. Sexual prejudice, like any other prejudice, is an attitude or a psychological predisposition that leads to negative evaluation of a social group or individual, resulting in hostility and dislike, leading to a defective retrieval system and making knowledge resources unattainable to marginalised people. Since its inception in 1970, one of the goals of the American Library Association's (ALA) GLBT Round Table has been to make library materials on gay, lesbian, bisexual, and transgender people easily accessible, with no ambiguity or bias (<https://www.ala.org/ala/glbtrt/>). In 1971, Joan Marshall and Steven Wolf, at the 1971 ALA meeting in Dallas, criticised sharply the sexist and homophobic labeling in the LCSH and in the DDC, later published in *Revolt of Librarians* (West & Katz, 1972).

In the same year, another important observation was made by Berman (1971), and he recommended the deletion of cross-reference to "sexual perversion" for both "homosexuality" and "lesbianism" (Berman, 1971). Berman and his associates also developed innovative subject headings on sexuality that were later adopted by many other libraries and also brought forth certain changes in LCSH through the Subject Authority Cooperative Programme (SACO). A controlled vocabulary is nothing but a set of terms universally applicable which a cataloguer or an indexer chooses for describing the subject content as there is exclusively one preferable term for each concept. Hence, in one sense, controlled vocabulary can be considered a universal language. It is axiomatic that the editors of LCSH and DDC must keep that in mind while naming various concepts of published works. But, unfortunately, this selection of terms often becomes a biased one. In the introduction part of the 1971 edition of the book, Berman points out that the main purpose of the subject heads is to assist scholars as well as common readers to find the right one from the printed collection in libraries, and it must have universality as knowledge and scholarship are universal and subject headings must serve a worldwide reading community (Berman, 1971, 1993). But unfortunately, what Berman found is that the LC list can only satisfy parochial jingoistic Europeans and North Americans of white hue, at least nominally Christian and preferably Protestant in faith, comfortably situated in the middle- and higher-income brackets, largely domiciled in suburbia, and fundamentally loyal to the established order who have deep faith only in the glory of Western civilization. Both the LC and Sears schema were designed for use in western libraries, and the racist and colonial bias were only natural. Broadly speaking, the subject heading schemes are nothing but late Victorian by-products.

Hope A. Olson, Associate Dean and Professor at the School of Information Studies at the University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee, begins her ground-breaking work entitled *Power to Name: Locating the Limits of Subject Representation in Libraries* with a reference to the experience of Virginia Woolf in the British Museum library (Olson, 1996, 2002, 2011). Olson tries to point out that classification pioneers like Melvil Dewey and Charles Cutter wanted to maintain control

and consistency by using rigid controlled vocabulary, and for this reason, they insisted on a universal language while naming various concepts in published works. Olson categorically pointed out that Dewey's and Cutter's insistence on this universal language in fact excludes and ignores "others," specifically all those people who are not "white, male, Eurocentric, Christocentric, heterosexual, able-bodied, bourgeois mainstream." Olson analyses selected subject headings related to race, gender, and ethnicity from DDC and LCSH and shows their shortcomings (Olson, 2011). Olson shows how FEMALE is the broader term and WOMEN (Status of Women, Abused Women, Abusive Women, Aged Women, etc.) becomes the narrower term and is placed in a lower position in the hierarchy. Therefore, in a hierarchical system, the "first term" is the most powerful one, and it is the product of the powerful class that rules the society and makes the classification. Another serious structural problem with classifications is their permanency. There is hardly any flexibility. Once a book is placed in a category, even a new category, it usually stays there (Olson, 2011).

Steven A. Knowlton in his work entitled "*Three Decades since Prejudices and Antipathy: A Study of Changes in the Library of Congress Subject Headings*," published in *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly*, reported that many of Berman's suggestions have been implemented. Of the 225 headings Berman suggested changes to, 88 (or 39%) have been changed almost exactly as he suggested, while an additional 54 (or 24%) have been changed in ways that partially reflect Berman's suggestions. Berman himself estimated that almost half of his proposed changes/suggestions have been accommodated in later editions of LCSH, while other headings remain unchanged. Around 80 items (36% of Berman's suggestions) remained unchanged till 2005 (Knowlton, 2005).

Emily Drabinski, in her article "Queering the Catalog: Queer Theory and the Politics of Representation," figured out that the bias in cataloguing is a functional problem for which materials are catalogued incorrectly and corrections can be made with correct pressure from activist cataloguers. She supports keeping even the "offensive terms" (in the present context) in the catalogue and believes correction should be done after proper education by the library educators. In 2018, Paige Crowl in her article "Queerly Categorized: LGBTQ+ Subjects and Language in the Catalogue" describes how she realises "queer materials are infamously difficult to find, especially for inexperienced searchers."

Brian M. Watson shows in his article entitled "*There was Sex but no Sexuality: Critical Cataloging and the Classification of Asexuality in LCSH*" shows how searching for terms like "asexuality" or "asexual" results in "Plants-Reproduction, Asexual." Watson also discusses critical *cataloguing* that depends more on catalogic warrant rather than bibliographic warrant, views catalogues in a "holistic manner" and analyses each term in the light of "potential harm or benefit" to the individual and to the community. Critical catalogers believe that LCC and DDC are "living documents" that can be "revised and improved."

As far as materials regarding LGBTQ people are concerned, their knowledge organisation is in motion. The identity group of transgender and gender-variant people is still in a state of

“acute formation”. The LGBTQ population is using new language every day; their vocabulary is changing every day. LC uses TRANSSEXUALS or TRANSEXUALITY, while people of the LGBTQ community think ‘TRANSGENDERED’ would be a more appropriate umbrella term. It is quite clear through these representative research works by the stalwarts that, till date, the Eurocentric white heterosexual male-dominated KOSs in libraries of any type or size overlook the needs of those underprivileged “others”. It also shows how these biases affect library tools in general, making access to queer materials (LGBTQIA+) difficult. It is also clear that no research has been conducted in India to assess the state-of-the-art, best practices, and organisational challenges for managing transgender knowledge resources in Indian academic libraries. A search in the OPAC of the National Library of India (Lesbian OR Gay OR Bisexual OR Transgender OR Queer OR Intersex OR Asexual) reveals that there are only 655 documents out of lakhs of documents in the catalogue, whereas, IndCat (the union catalogue of Indian Universities with 1,82,25,339 records from 206 universities in India) shows only 1200 records with the same search query.

2.2. What Went Wrong with the Domain-Specific Vocabularies?

There are numerous initiatives to develop glossaries and term dictionaries by individuals and groups, subject guides by libraries, and term definitions by experts in the domain of LGBTQIA. Initiatives such as the LGBTQIA Resource Center’s glossary (<https://lgbtqia.ucdavis.edu/educated/glossary/>); terminology developed by the LGBTQ+ Center (<https://lgbtq.wfu.edu/resources/lgbtq-terminology/>); terminology developed by the LGBT Resource Center of the University of California, San Francisco (<https://lgbt.ucsf.edu/>); LGBT terms adopted by New Jersey Institute of Technology from Montclair State University and the GLAAD Media Reference Guide-11th Edition ([glaad.org/reference](http://www.glaad.org/reference)); a structured subject headings as developed by Yale University Library (<https://guides.library.yale.edu/c.php?g=295883&p=1972812>) are quite well known activities in the domain. On the other hand, the individual efforts like the list of LGBT terms as compiled by David Sweetnam (<https://getintoenglish.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/LBGTQI-Gay-Vocabulary.pdf>); a broad compilation of the LGBTQIA terms from LCSH by a librarian named Netanel Ganin (<http://www.netanelgan.com/projects/QueerLCSH/QueerLCSH.html>); Queer in Action Dictionary by Michael Schramm (michigandaily.com/uncategorized/queer-action-lgbt-z-dictionary/); and the complications of a list of available GLBT Controlled Vocabulary by Matt Johnson of the American Library Association (ALA) in 2007 and its later modification by Jessica L. Colbert in 2017 (ala.org/rt/popularresources/vocab) are significant contributions. But in general, these lists/glossaries/vocabularies are not adequate and not structured as per the latest standards in KOSs. The first structured approach in the compilation of a proper LGBTQIA+ vocabulary system on the basis of the standards of the domain like SKOS and ISO-25964 has been started with the development of The Homosaurus (<http://homosaurus.org/>) - an international linked data vocabulary of LGBTQ terms by K.J. Rawson (the director of the Digital Transgender Archive). It is now available as Linked Open Data (LOD) and is being revised continuously by members of the editorial board. It is also

possible to use Homosaurus as a source for subject headings in MARC records (MARC source code is homoit) e.g. - 650 7 \$a Non-binary people. \$2 homoit

The Homosaurus, as a domain-specific vocabulary control device (Hardesty & Nolan, 2021) is much more comprehensive in comparison with LCSH (see Table 1), and many library systems are using Homosaurus for the purpose of populating subject access fields for LGBTQIA+ related documents (see – ccslib.org/Catalogers/index.php/Homosaurus_Subject_Headings).

Table 1: Comprehensiveness of Homosaurus vocabulary

LCSH Terms	Homosaurus Terms
Older sexual minorities	Older lesbians Older queer people Older bisexual people Older gay men Older (LGBTQ)
Gender non-conforming people	Agender people Non-binary people Pangender people
Closeted gays	Closeted bisexual people Closeted gay men Closeted lesbians

The Homosaurus (Zwaaf, 2020) is a comprehensive KOS for the LGBTQIA+ domain, available in the public domain, and supports different RDF serializing export formats (like N-Triples, JSON-LD & TTL), but unfortunately not free from some serious limitations like – a) no provision for multilingual labels, and therefore cannot be claimed as an international standard; b) not collaborative in nature, and therefore cannot be claimed as a global platform; c) no scope for indicating language labels, and therefore not fully compliant with the LOD standards (see Table 2).

Table 2: Non-compliant nature of Homosaurus for multilingual labels

Homosaurus SKOS entry	Multi-lingual SKOS entry
< https://homosaurus.org/v3/homoit0001671 > < http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#prefLabel > "Xenogender people" .	skos:prefLabel "Xenogender people"@en, "জেনোজেন্ডার মানুষ"@bn, "ज़ेनोज़ेन्डर लोग"@hi

The limitations of Homosaurus as indicated above are not due to the content quality or editorial policies related to the development of Homosaurus as an international linked open data but perhaps because of the container structure and the software platform it is using to develop and deliver Homosaurus as a linked open dataset (Cifor& Rawson, 2022). An inquiry to the Homosaurus board reveals that it is using a custom Ruby on Rails application based on Oregon Digital's Controlled Vocabulary Manager (see - github.com/OregonDigital/ControlledVocabularyManager).

3. Objectives

This research work is an attempt to develop mechanisms for building a collaborative, multilingual, and Skos-compliant vocabulary control system for the LGBTQIA+ domain on the basis of the existing Homosaurus project. It will support participation from LIS professionals, subject specialists, and social activists across the world. The specific objectives are as follows:

- 3.1 To create a prototype vocabulary control system that will use the current Homosaurus linked open vocabulary as its foundation and will grant registered members privilege-based access to perform development, maintenance, and translation activities subject to the final approval of the superusers (board members);
- 3.2 To design the prototype to support easy translation of different Skos labels, scope notes, rdfs comments, etc in different languages through Unicode-compliant language tools and by following the Skos structure for language labeling (see Table 2); and
- 3.3 To transfer the completed multilingual vocabulary system for the LGBTQIA+ domain from the development platform to the Skos browser for easy retrieval and API access (to ensure cross-system utilities).

4. Methods and Tools

The objectives, as specified in the previous section, need a two-layer solution to achieve the goals. Layer 1 deals with the development of a platform to accommodate Homosaurus as a linked open vocabulary. It must have provisions for web-based registration to the system, a mechanism to control the privileges of the registered users for addition, deletion, modification, and translation of the terms on the basis of the guiding principles as prescribed by the editorial board members.

Layer 1 of the system should have facilities to add new terms (as concepts, narrower terms, broader terms, related terms, hidden labels, etc), to add translations of the existing terms/ concepts/scope notes/comments in different languages, and to store the vocabulary data as RDF triples (preferably in a backend graph database compliant with RDF and SPARQL). Apart from these features, layer 1 supports efficient management of publication workflow through the facilities of storing history of editing and validation of add/edit/deletion/modification of the terms added to the base vocabulary.

Layer 2, on the other hand, supports the porting of the completed multilingual vocabulary, developed through collaboration, into a Skos browser supported by the semantic web framework at the backend. The two-layer software architecture with the open source candidate software for different activities is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The proposed software architecture with component open source software

Layer 1 (organization) is comprised of two open source software components: GraphDB as the backend RDF triple store and VocBench as a linked open vocabulary control platform. The layer 2 (access part) takes the input from the layer 1 in RDF serializing formats (N3, Turtle, RDF), and stores the imported vocabulary in the semantic web framework (open source Apache Jena Fuseki) component. The Skosmos, a Skos browser, is acting as the front-end to support access to the multilingual LGBTQIA+ vocabulary either by the end users (search, browse, display, export) or by a software agent through a REST/API mechanism. The details of the component software along with their major roles are appended in Table 3.

Table 3: Components of the framework and their major roles

Layer	Tools	Roles
Layer 1 Organization	Skosify (github.com/NatLibFi/Skosify)	Generates a clean SKOS file from input through cleaning, validating and enriching on the basis of the SKOS specification and best practices.
	RDF Validator (w3.org/RDF/Validator/)	A tool from w3C that checks integrity of a RDF file. A strict validation of the file generated through Skosify is required.
	GraphDB – Free edition (ontotext.com/products/graphdb)	An extensively adopted RDF store and/or Graph DBMS system for storing RDF triples, and act as the backend for the VocBench vocabulary control system.
	VocBench – version 3.x (vocbench.uniroma2.it)	A web based open source platform to support development of SKOS/SKOS-XL compliant thesaurus, OWL based ontologies etc in a collaborative and Unicode-compliant multilingual environment.
	Semantic Turkey (semanticturkey.uniroma2.it)	An open source service platform for knowledge management for RDF family of standards (RDF/RDFS/OWL/SKOS/SKOSXL). VocBench includes it as a component.
Layer 2 Access	Fuseki (jena.apache.org/documentation/fuseki2/)	Fuseki is a SPARQL server and RDF triple store. It is the recommended backend for Skosmos (the front-end of the linked open vocabulary system).
	Skosmos (skosmos.org/)	Skosmos is an open source web-enabled publication platform for Skos-compliant vocabularies with the provision for SPARQL endpoints and REST/API based integration.

The minute details of the methodology for developing the entire platform right from installation and configuration of the components to the organization and publication of the LGBTQIA+ vocabulary are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The workflow in the framework

5. Features of the Organization Layer

Layer 1 (mainly VocBench) of the framework supports defining the scheme and its properties, data types, classes, and concepts related to a given vocabulary. The vocabulary can be imported in a variety of RDF formats. It allows base URI declaration, model specification (RDFS/OWL/SKOS/OntoLex/EDOAL), lexicalization selection (RDFS/SKOS/SKOS-XL/OntoLex), history and validation triggering during the initial stage of vocabulary design. It has provision for determining repository access (CreateLocal/CreateRemote/AccessExistingRemote), description of remote server URL (for this research work, a remote GraphDB server is available on a departmental LAN at <http://192.168.1.93:7200>), data repository

configuration, and so on at the time of project creation. Once the validated RDF formatted vocabulary imported inside the project, a set of privileged users (as determined by the system administrator) can add concepts, labels (skos:prefLabel, skos:altLabel, skos:hiddenLabel), semantic relationships (skos:broader, skos:narrower, skos:related), mapping relationships (skos:exactMatch, skos:closeMatch, skos:broadMatch, skos:narrowMatch, skos:relatedMatch, rdfs:seeAlso), documentary notes (skos:note, skos:scopeNote, skos:definition, skos:example, skos:historyNote, skos:editorialNote, skos:changeNote), Dublin Core properties (dct:title, dct:creator, dct:descriptionetc), notations (skos:notation), if required, and other properties (like rdfs:label, rdfs:comment). The provisions for adding translations with respective language label for all the above stated elements are available in the system (see Figure 4). After completion of the project vocabulary, users can place queries through the inbuilt SPARQL query editor of the system (based on the YASGUI editor). The completed project (vocabulary) can be exported into a number of RDF serializing formats (RDF/XML, JSON-LD, N3, N-Triples, Turtle and so on), Spreadsheet serializing format (XLSX), and Zthes serializing format (XML). The other enhanced features of the system are the validation subsystem (accept/reject/validate), history of editing (shows commits and allows sorting and filtering of commit histories), tools for alignment validation (management of alignment from two different sources), custom form generation (a powerful mechanism to provide a declarative specification of the key elements of a given vocabulary), resource metadata description (project custom DC based metadata as per the needs), and facilitates like data-oriented graph generation, Sheet2RDF, SKOS diffing etc (Stellato et al, 2015, 2017, 2020).

Figure 4: Term editing facilities in the framework

The screenshot displays the Skos browser interface for the term 'Xenogender people'. The interface is divided into several sections:

- Header:** 'LGBTQIA CMSLOV' and 'Content language English' with a search bar.
- Navigation:** 'Alphabetical', 'Hierarchy', and 'New' tabs. Below them are letter-based navigation links (A-Z, 0-9).
- Left Sidebar:** A list of related terms and redirects, including 'X assigned at birth', 'X-rated films (LGBTQ)', 'Xenogender identity', and 'Xenogender people'.
- Main Content Area:**
 - PREFERRED TERM:** 'Xenogender people' with a copy icon.
 - RELATED CONCEPTS:** 'Non-binary people' and 'Xenogender identity'.
 - DESCRIPTION:** 'A person who identifies their gender in relation to non-human understandings of gender and relates to animals, plants, or other things.'
 - IDENTIFIER:** 'lgbtqiaccmslov0001671'.
 - DATE ISSUED:** '6/30/21'.
 - REPLACES:** '<http://homosaurus.org/v2/xenogenderPeople>'.
 - IN OTHER LANGUAGES:**

জেনোজেন্ডার মানুষ	Bangla
जेनोजेन्डर लोग	Hindi
 - URI:** '<https://lgbtqia-cmslov.org/v1/lgbtqiaccmslov0001671>' with a copy icon.
 - DOWNLOAD THIS CONCEPT:** 'RDF/XML TURTLE JSON-LD' and 'Last modified 12/8/21'.

Figure 5: Term access in Skos browser

Layer 2 (mainly Skosmos) of the framework supports access to the completed vocabulary in the public domain. Skosmos allows publication of any number of Skos-compliant vocabularies through an intuitive user interface, having facilities to display terms (along with redirection) alphabetically, hierarchically, along with the tab for displaying the newly added terms (Suominen et al, 2014, 2015). The term display includes almost all essential components such as preferred term, related concepts, term description, term identifier, date of creation and modifications, statement of term replacement (if any), terms in other languages (alternate skos: prefLabel), term URI, and provision for end users to download the term network in different RDF serialising formats (see Figure 5).

Another interesting feature in Skosmos in browsing and searching by a set of given languages (can be configured to add languages according to the needs). The cross-collection multilingual search in Skosmos is quite a comprehensive feature, which is supported by the backend Fuseki(jena-text index for searching).

Figure 6: Multi-lingual search across the vocabulary publication platform

7. Conclusion

Digital humanities encompasses more than the use of ICT-enabled tools and techniques in humanities teaching, learning, and research. It has all the potential to reach the unreached, to explore new research areas, to travel uncharted paths, and to promote social inclusivity. It can provide a much-needed platform for domain experts, social activists, ordinary people, students, and researchers from all over the world to collaborate to push the boundaries of the humanities. LIS professionals, as tech-savvy knowledge managers, have additional roles in designing the platform, developing the inclusive knowledge base, and promoting interaction and collaboration at a global scale to support knowledge creation. The three-fold objectives of this research work (as given in section 3) have been achieved and demonstrated through a number of relevant snapshots of the system. The organizing layer of the framework is managed mainly by the VocBench, and it allows remote registration by users through a web interface, subsequent permission by the administrator to include the registered user inside the system, and the allocation of privileges and responsibilities to work as contributors or editors for a given vocabulary. This mechanism ensures global-scale collaboration. VocBench extends a number of features in developing and maintaining Skos-compliant vocabularies (explained in section 5), including translation of the labels into different languages through Unicode-compliant language tools. Therefore, the second objective as specified has also been achieved. The access layer of the framework, handled by the Skosmos browser, has extended the required facilities to achieve

the third objective: to ensure retrieval of the LGBTQIA+ vocabulary in the public domain with the facility to browse (alphabetically and hierarchically) and search (English, Hindi, Bengali, any included language). The access layer of the framework can also response (in JSON format) against REST/API call in multilingual environment (see Figure 7), and thereby ensures seamless integration of the vocabulary server with the ILSs (like Koha) or DLSs (like DSpace, Eprints archive etc) for populating subject access fields in the data entry framework.

```

@context:
  skos: "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#"
  uri: "@id"
  type: "@type"
  onki: "http://schema.onki.fi/onki#"
  results:
    @id: "onki:results"
    prefLabel: "skos:prefLabel"
    altLabel: "skos:altLabel"
    hiddenLabel: "skos:hiddenLabel"
  result:
    @:
      uri: "https://lgbtqia-cmslov.org/v1/lgbtqiaccmslov0001671"
      type:
        @: "skos:Concept"
      localname: "lgbtqiaccmslov0001671"
      prefLabel: "ज़ेनोजेन्डर लोग"
      lang: "hi"
      vocab: "cmslov"

```

Figure 7: REST/API response in access layer

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